

Draft template for data and information collection about solutions

#	Requested information/data	Comment
1: Driver / pain point		
1.1	What is the solution	Short description
1.2	What is the TRL of the solution	According to https://shorturl.at/qIWZ6
1.3	Main driver: <input type="checkbox"/> Legislation <input type="checkbox"/> Fulfilling policy goals <input type="checkbox"/> Economic reason <input type="checkbox"/> Pollution reduction <input type="checkbox"/> Other: _____	Tick one
1.4	Describe in detail the driver(s) for the establishing of the supply chain	Including secondary drivers / pain points
1.5	Why do you propose this solution to be promoted by CiNURGi?	Please highlight special advantages of the solution in terms of economy, environment and climate. In the answer, please mention what you consider the innovative aspects of the proposed solution, and in which geographical perspective.
1.6	Proposer	Name, organization, contact details
2: The biomass waste material		
2.1	Location of the biomass waste, its collection and handling	Address or geographical location
2.2	Who is the biomass stakeholder	Key contact person and, if relevant, the company
2.3	What is the type of biomass waste	2.1: Location of the processing plant (Address or geographical location)
2.4	Which amounts are collected on an annual basis in terms of volume/ton, kg N and P	

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2.5	How is the biomass waste collected?	
2.6	How is the biomass stored?	
2.7	How is the biomass delivered to the processing plant?	
2.8	What is the intermediary and final costs of the biomass waste?	Including details on costs for collection, storage, handling, gate fees, subsidies, ...
2.9	Describe the environmental problems that the collection avoids	Type of emissions avoided, focusing on N and P
2.10	Describe the greenhouse gas emissions avoided	Laughing gas, methane, CO ₂
3: The processing		
3.1	Location of the processing	Address or geographical location
3.2	Who is the processing stakeholder	Key contact person and, if relevant, the company)
3.3	Please describe the processing technology or the cascade of processing technologies	No details needed, mainly the names of the technologies used. A flow diagram showing the various steps in the processing would be envisaged.
3.4	Inputs in processing technology in addition to the raw material	Energy, water, chemical, etc.
3.5	What are intermediary products, end products and waste products from the processing	Descriptions must include mass balances (ton per year) and the chemical content of each product, as a minimum for N and P. A Sankey diagram would be envisaged, also including the abovementioned input materials consumed.
3.6	What is the intermediary and final costs of the BBF?	Including details on costs for collection, storage, handling, gate fees, subsidies, ...
3.7	Describe the environmental emissions that the BBF production causes	The emissions related to N and P, including ammonia emissions, leaching, runoff and percolation of N and P

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3.8	Describe the greenhouse gas emissions avoided	Laughing gas, methane, CO ₂
3.9	Describe possible effects of the processing on plant availability of N and P	
4: The BBF		
4.1	Responsible for BBF handling and logistics	Address or geographical location
4.2	Who is the BBF handling stakeholder	Key contact person and, if relevant, the company
4.3	Is any further processing of the BBF made before marketing?	Including packaging
4.4	How is the BBF stored?	
4.5	Where is the BBF marketed and in which volumes?	Who are the customers
4.6	What is the intermediary cost and final end-user price for the BBF?	Including details on costs for collection, storage, handling, gate fees, subsidies, ...
4.7	Describe the environmental emissions that the BBF handling causes	The emissions related to N and P, including ammonia emissions, leaching, runoff and percolation of N and P
4.8	Describe the greenhouse gas emissions caused	Laughing gas, methane, CO ₂ , including for delivery to the end-user